

Programmable Packet-Optical Networks Security and Monitoring using DPUs with Embedded GPU (Invited)

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Compiled December 18, 2025

Data Processing Unit (DPU) with embedded Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) have the potential to revolutionize optical network functionalities at the edge. These advanced units can significantly enhance the performance and capabilities of optical networks by integrating powerful processing capabilities directly at the network edge, where data is generated and consumed. We explore the use cases for DPUs in optical data monitoring with local AI processing and embedded security. This paradigm shift aims to enable more efficient data handling, reduced latency, and improved overall network performance by leveraging local AI processing capabilities embedded within DPUs.

In this paper, we show how DPUs can analyze vast amounts of optical data in real-time, implementing advanced data analysis algorithms and security protocols directly on the DPUs to provide robust monitoring and protection for the optical networks. Results indicate that DPUs with embedded GPUs can significantly improve the detection and response times to network anomalies, performance issues, and security threats.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1364/ao.XX.XXXXX>

1. INTRODUCTION

Edge computing allows stakeholders to keep their IT infrastructures, Machine Learning (ML), Artificial Intelligence (AI) processing, and service management close to where data is generated and used. To accomplish this goal, edge computing resources must possess advanced networking capabilities, including ultra-high bandwidth connectivity.

Edge nodes interact with each other and with the cloud through switches/routers served by high-speed optical transmission systems. Network Interface Card (NIC)s provide such connectivity to nearby routers. In just a few years, the capacity of NICs has significantly increased, advancing from 10 Gb/s to 400 Gb/s and beyond. Furthermore, they evolved to Data Processing Unit (DPU)s, i.e., powerful network computing systems encompassing hardware accelerators for advanced networking and embedded security [1–3]. DPUs, also known as SmartNICs, were initially developed for use within data centers. However, they are now being recognized as valuable candidate tools for enhancing the networking capabilities of edge computing infrastructures. DPUs, which are now commercially available with speeds of up to 400Gb/s, have recently been equipped with

integrated Graphics Processing Unit (GPU)s, enabling new AI processing capabilities on networking data.

In parallel with the evolution from NIC to DPU, also optical transmission systems have significantly evolved, enhancing from standalone legacy network equipment (i.e., transponders and muxponders) to small form-factor transceivers. In particular, transceivers adopting the coherent technology can nowadays be inserted directly within routers and switches and used to communicate across hundreds of km at an extremely high rate (i.e., 400Gb/s and beyond).

In this paper, we propose the adoption of DPUs equipped with GPU and coherent pluggable transceivers, expanding upon the works which assume basic SmartNICs in the context of optical networks [1–3]. We present the benefits obtained through this converged system including computing, networking, and optical technologies specifically focusing on the case where basic smartNIC/DPUs are enhanced with embedded GPU to support secure packet-optical communication.

Initially, we present an overview of the enabling technologies, specifically DPUs and coherent pluggable transceivers. Next, we explore the expected benefits in terms of security and monitoring in converged infrastructures that are ideal for cutting-edge,

energy-efficient, and fast solutions in the context of beyond 5G networks.

Specifically, the contributions of this work are:

- We propose and assess the use of DPUs with embedded GPUs for optical networks. This integration enhances the processing capabilities at the network edge, enabling more efficient and powerful network data handling.
- We implement and integrate embedded AI-based monitoring and security features within the DPUs. We conducted a comprehensive performance evaluation to compare the inference times of setups using DPU with GPU versus setups using DPU with CPU only.
- We develop an experimental testbed to validate proposed approaches for real-time measurements and comparisons of prediction inference times, demonstrating the practical applicability and effectiveness of the integrated DPU with GPU solution.

2. RELATED WORK

A. Related work on AI/ML solutions for optical networks

In this subsection we highlight several valuable works proposing and validating the use of AI processing applied to optical networks.

The study [4] employed Remote Procedure Calls (gRPC) telemetry and a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to collect received signal data from whitebox transponders. Moreover, they have shown that it is feasible to classify field fibre bending in real-time using this approach. The study conducted by Tanimura et al. [5] utilises signal data acquired from digital coherent optical receivers as input data and employs a CNN for learning. Their study focuses on using this data for Optical Signal to Noise Ratio (OSNR) calculation and identifying the modulation format and symbol rate. The implementation of this methodology has led to exceptional categorization accuracy. Fan et al. [6] achieved successful identification of both the bitrate and modulation scheme for on-off keying signals by employing DNN-based multitask learning, which allows for the simultaneous identification of several parameters. Furthermore, they detected the OSNR, Chromatic Dispersion (CD), and differential group delay, alongside Optical Performance Monitoring (OPM). The CNN utilised asynchronous delay-tap sampling as an input parameter in this experiment. Jargon et al. [7] showed that training a neural network with properties derived from the geometry of a constellation can enable the estimation of unknown transmission characteristics, such as the CD and OSNR. Prior studies have investigated the use of neural networks to estimate the OSNR by eliminating nonlinear noise sources that impact the OSNR [8]. Machine learning can also be utilised for estimating parameters that are not limited to the OSNR. In their study, Fan et al. [6] demonstrated that the error vector magnitude can be accurately predicted for different modulation formats by feeding the decoded data of coherent signals into a CNN. A comprehensive analysis in [9] has extensively examined various machine learning approaches to estimate the OSNR, Q-factor, Bit Error Rate (BER), and other quality of transmission (QoT) metrics. These approaches have been applied in a wide range of applications, including optical communication lines, optical amplifiers, and networks. Recent research has focused on estimating the transmission properties associated with the

distance direction of optical fibre transmission lines. The fiber-longitudinal optical power profile of a multi-span optical fibre transmission line is evaluated in representative research [10] by analysing the waveform data received by a digital coherent optical receiver and recreating the transmitted waveform. Until recently, these tasks were exclusively implemented using Optical Time Domain Reflectometer (OTDR). However, OTDRs have several drawbacks, such as their difficulty in being applied to multi-span optical fibre transmission lines. On the other hand, these techniques, which can calculate the location of optical power reduction without the need for specialised tools, show great potential for achieving extremely precise optical power measurements. Moreover, as a result of OPM, advancements in machine learning are transforming the methods and procedures of operations and maintenance. The conventional approach has been to employ reactive measures, such as altering routes, in response to failures. Nevertheless, the idea of utilising machine learning to identify indications of subtle malfunction and taking proactive measures to replace equipment before a genuine failure transpires has been introduced [11]. In order to comprehend this, it is imperative to scrutinise the data acquired by OPM, identify any instances of soft failure, and investigate the underlying causes of failure. Shahkarami et al. [12] utilized machine learning techniques to detect and identify soft failures in multi-span optical fiber transmission lines, namely by analyzing the Bit Error Rate (BER). Mayer et al. [13] showed that real-time soft failure localization may be achieved using a neural network. This is done by collecting the OSNR and input/output power data from the complete network through streaming telemetry. The work in [14] proposes a multi-task CNN for advanced multi-parameter monitoring.

All these works show the potential and effective use of AI/ML solutions applied to optical networks. They typically rely on external processing resources implemented e.g. in centralized cloud systems. The introduction of DPUs equipped with embedded GPU and coherent optical transceivers, as proposed in this work, opens the way to the deployment of such solutions in a decentralized and possibly federated scenario, implemented where optical monitoring data are generated and where computed actions can be directly enforced with no communication delay.

B. Related work on network security and traffic classification

In this subsection we highlight relevant works proposing and validating the use of network programmability/accelerators and deep packet inspection (DPI) applied to cyber security and traffic classification.

The work in [15] proposes anomaly-based methodologies for developing a unique pattern for detecting and identifying Distributed Denial of Services (DDoS) attacks. Signatures-based solutions are indeed preferred over anomaly detection due to their superior efficiency. An Access Control List (ACL) could be created based on the signature to automatically prevent future attacks that match the signature. Zhang et al. [16] conducted a study on enhancing the performance of the Snort 3.0 IDS by utilizing the Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK). The researchers determined that employing DPDK to enhance and augment the detection rate of Snort effectively resolves the performance concerns. This is accomplished through the implementation of an alternative packet polling technique, reduced CPU interruptions, and a decrease in memory operations. Qinwen et al. [17] conducted a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of three IDS Snort, Bro, and Suricata. In [17], crucial parameters are

examined, such as the utilization of system resources, the processing of packets, and the rate at which packets are dropped, that restrict the effectiveness of network intrusion detection system (NIDS) in handling high volumes of traffic in large-scale networks. The limits were determined by the implementation of the following experiments: the default setup, optimizations of the detection method, and modifications to the DAQ configuration to enhance capture performance. The results suggest that specific pattern-matching algorithms will reduce a substantial volume of traffic. Utilizing Suricata, the CPU use is significantly elevated when employing pattern-matching methods, while the NIDSs consume a small number of memory resources. Qinwen et al. [18] addressed the challenges associated with open-source intrusion detection systems in high-speed networks in their publication. A data transfer rate of 60Gbps is achieved by utilizing a transparent Intrusion Detection System (IDS) in conjunction with eXpress Data Path (XDP). Suricata would initiate and discard packets when the data rate reaches 60 Gb/s. In addition, they attempted to identify malevolent behavior using a solitary rule. At this juncture, they see that employing a solitary rule is inadequate for identifying malevolent behavior. Their research suggests utilizing hardware acceleration techniques to collect traffic on 100Gb/s networks. In 2018, Yang et al. introduced an architecture for regular expression (RE) matching that processes several bytes simultaneously. The architecture incorporates the benefits of three Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA)-based algorithms, namely Simple State Merge Tree (SSMT), Distribute Data in Round-Robin (DDRR), and Multipath Speculation, to enhance the speed of matching. Despite being memory frugal, they achieved a processing speed of 140Gbps on a FPGA.

Many DPI methods are proposed to classify network traffic. Libprotoident [19] is a DPI library that identifies application layer protocols for network flows. Unlike other methods that require capturing the entire packet payload, Libprotoident only uses the first four bytes of payload sent in each direction, the size of the first payload-bearing packet in each direction, and the TCP or UDP port numbers for the flow. The nDPI library, cited as [20], provides application-layer detection of protocols that is independent of the port being used. This allows for the identification of known protocols on non-standard ports, as well as the detection of unknown protocols. Both ntop and nProbe utilize nDPI for this purpose. OpenDPI [21] is a software library that is built upon the commercial PACE product from Ipoque. It uses a combination of behavioral and statistical analysis techniques to identify transmission types of applications in monitored traffic. Behavioral analysis involves searching for known behavioral patterns of an application in the monitored traffic, while statistical analysis calculates statistical indicators that can be used to identify transmission types. DPI faces a major limitation with encrypted traffic. The reason is that it obstructs access to the underlying data, which makes it difficult to perform DPI effectively [22]. Chen et al. [23] proposed an FPGA-based approach for intrusion detection in cloud systems, which offloads detection tasks to FPGA-based SmartNICs for improved efficiency and reduced overhead. This model achieves high throughput, low latency, and high detection accuracy while providing benefits such as improved scalability and reduced power consumption. Although the paper has limitations, such as limited evaluation and lack of comparison with other FPGA-based approaches, it presents an innovative solution to the limitations of software-based intrusion detection in cloud systems. Further research and development could significantly enhance cloud systems and datacenter security. Wang et al. [24] presented

an interesting approach to intrusion detection using extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) technology in the Linux kernel, but some potential limitations should be considered. Firstly, the effectiveness is decreased on larger networks with higher traffic volumes, which could limit its scalability. Secondly, false positives and negatives are not addressed. Finally, the paper does not evaluate the potential overhead of the system on system resources, such as CPU and memory usage. These limitations should be considered when considering the feasibility and applicability of the proposed system in real-world scenarios. Kim et al. [25] proposed a real-time network intrusion detection system that uses a deferred decision and hybrid classifier approach to improve detection accuracy and reduce false alarms. The authors provide a comprehensive overview of the system architecture and implementation details, and the experimental results show promising results on a publicly available dataset.

3. ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES

A. DPU

A DPU is a dedicated hardware component engineered to provide rapid data processing capabilities. DPUs are commonly used in data centers, server configurations, and supercomputers. However, there is increasing interest in exploring their potential use in Telco and edge networking applications. DPUs provide the ability to handle data transport, storage, and processing for huge datasets. This allows for fast computations and supports real-time analysis and acceleration of data-intensive applications. Unlike typical NICs that primarily prioritize low-level protocol acceleration, such as Ethernet, and depend on the server's CPUs for other networking activities, DPUs have the benefit of programmability at higher layers. They have the ability to directly perform complex activities within the network, thereby releasing processing resources for tenant and application services.

The latest DPU iteration has a maximum of four connections functioning at rates of up to 400 Gb/s. These DPUs also possess timing and synchronization capabilities, hardware encryption, and integrated security measures. In addition, they are equipped with a maximum of 16 ARM CPUs to manage embedded computer tasks. The most recent iteration also incorporates integrated GPU capabilities. DPUs often utilize flat-top connections such as OSFP and QSFP112/56/28 form factors rather than the QSFP-DD form factor found in packet-optical switches that support coherent pluggable modules. Nevertheless, the next iteration of coherent transceivers designed to meet these specific dimensions has already been declared for a speed of 100Gbps. Additionally, future generations of SmartNICs are anticipated to also be compatible with QSFP-DD, enabling speeds of 400Gbps and beyond.

B. DOCA SDK

NVIDIA's DOCA (Data Center-on-a-Chip Architecture) is a software development framework designed for the BlueField DPUs. It includes libraries, service agents, and reference applications and supports C programming and DPDK for efficient packet processing. DOCA provides dedicated APIs for implementing IPsec, encryption, and decryption, making it easier for developers to integrate these functionalities into their applications.

A key component of DOCA is the DOCA Flow library, which enables the customization of packet processing by defining matching criteria and actions. These match-action units are organized in pipes and can be chained together for flexibility. DOCA leverages `rte_flow` to transmit rules to the embedded switch

(NIC switch) using NVIDIA's proprietary ASAP2 technology, offloading hardware traffic efficiently.

An example DOCA application for URL filtering involves creating OvS bridges and connecting scalable functions (SF). SFs are lightweight functions with dedicated queues for packet transmission and reception, similar to virtual functions (VFs) used in SR-IOV. The OvS bridges are hardware offloaded, with one connecting the physical port to the application (OvS-BR2) and another connecting the application to the host (OvS-BR1). Incoming packets on the physical port are forwarded to the application running on the CPU cores.

URL filtering entails parsing the application layer to locate the URL in the HTTP header. The SmartNIC utilizes a regular expression (RegEx) hardware accelerator to scan for the URL, significantly faster than CPU scanning. A third bridge can be created to enable user management of the application, with BlueField providing gRPC interfaces for runtime configuration.

C. Optical Transceiver Technology

For more than ten years, the rise in capacity in optical networks has mostly been achieved by developing successive generations of coherent optical transceivers that have better capacity and improved spectral efficiency (SE). In the past, coherent optical transceivers were typically integrated onto line cards, with the goal of optimizing both capacity and reach [26]. The boxes served as a physical barrier between the transport layer and the Ethernet/IP layer. They connected to switches and routers using grey short-reach transceivers, as depicted in Figure 1. The demarcation aligns with the internal structure of the majority of network operators, who typically maintain distinct teams responsible for managing the transport and IP network domains [27]. A significant advancement in coherent optical transceivers is their availability in pluggable form factors rather than being integrated into line cards. The OpenZR+ MSA [28] has expanded the range of uses for coherent pluggable optical transceivers by enabling the support of Ethernet client signals over extended distances in mesh optical networks that utilize reconfigurable optical add/drop multiplexer (ROADM) nodes. This development follows the 400ZR standard [29]. In addition, the OpenROADM MSA [30] has expanded the range of clients that can be transferred to include the optical transport network (OTN). There are two primary network designs that can be used to make use of coherent pluggable transceivers. The initial configuration maintains the specialised line cards, which currently support coherent pluggable transceivers such as C form-factor pluggable (CFP2) [31] or Quad small form-factor pluggable double density (QSFP-DD) [32]. This architecture preserves the distinct separation between transport and IP networks, making it well-suited for network operators who handle a variety of client traffic types. The second architecture takes advantage of the fact that high-capacity routers can naturally accommodate coherent pluggable transceivers in the QSFP-DD form factor. This eliminates the need for dedicated line cards and reduces the number of grey transceivers required. This allows for the efficient implementation of the IP-over-dense wavelength division multiplexing (DWDM) architecture that has been planned for a long time but has not yet been realized [33].

In this work, we assume coherent optical transceiver will be encompassed within SmartNICs/DPUs, overcoming current technological limitations (mainly due to power consumption and dissipation) that today prevent the effective deployment of such converged solution.

Fig. 1. The traditional optical network setup (top) involves aggregation routers and standalone transponders. In the evolved scenario (center), white box and coherent transceivers are utilized. The innovative optical metro network scenario incorporates edge computing nodes and DPUs with coherent transceivers (bottom).

4. INNOVATIVE EDGE-CLOUD SCENARIO

In this section, we present the innovative edge scenario potentially enabled by the introduction of DPUs with embedded GPU and coherent transceivers.

The delivery of 5G/6G services is indeed driving Telco Central Offices (COs) to host not only networking equipment such as routers but also edge computing resources. The separation of networking and computing resources comes at a cost: it is power-hungry, expensive (both in terms of CAPEX and OPEX), and inefficient with respect to latency, as multiple OEO conversions must be experienced in the computing continuum between 5G/6G services and edge and cloud resources.

Figure 1(top) shows a traditional network scenario where an edge computing node receives connectivity from a legacy router. The router, equipped with grey interfaces, rely on standalone transponders to communicate across the optical metro network to the Cloud. Thanks to the introduction of coherent pluggable transceivers, of type point-to-point or point-to-multipoint, transponders and aggregation routers can be eliminated as standalone elements, enabling a direct connection from the router to the optical metro infrastructure to towards the Cloud. This way, IP routers equipped with coherent pluggable modules (i.e., IPoDWDM) are driving the design and implementation of low-cost converged packet optical transport solutions, effectively removing boundaries between different IP and optical network domains, as shown in Figure 1(center).

Edge computing nodes encompassing DPUs equipped with coherent transceivers have the potential to further improve the edge-to-cloud continuum by removing the barriers between computing and networking resources, as shown in Figure 1(bottom). One benefit is the reduction of active standalone nodes and the necessity for intermediate Optical-Electrical-Optical (OEO)

conversions between the edge computing node and the cloud.

The second advantage pertains to reducing delay. This is accomplished by consolidating computational and optical network resources into a unified platform, resulting in a decrease in overall latency. Incorporating high-speed transceivers directly into DPUs will greatly improve the provision of ultra-low latency services for access. This will also allow for the utilization of hardware-accelerated network operations within DPUs, such as encryption. Furthermore, the presence of embedded DPU has the potential to significantly improve networking capabilities and performance by introducing AI processing at DPU.

These advantages can result in enhanced performance for both low-latency consumer apps and Telco infrastructure components. For instance, they can enable the implementation of 5G capabilities in proximity to cellular sites. Functions such as UPF-DU-CU could be relocated in close proximity to the cell site and consolidated on robust edge nodes, utilizing (i) hardware-accelerated networking solutions offered by DPUs (e.g., deep packet inspection, cyber security, encryption) and (ii) direct peer-to-peer optical connections to cloud services and point-to-multipoint connections to multiple RUs. In addition, embedded GPUs provide efficient and rapid AI-driven predictive and proactive capabilities [34]

5. PROPOSED SYSTEM MODEL FOR EMBEDDED SECURITY AND MONITORING

In this section, we introduce our comprehensive edge network system architecture, depicted in Figure 2, designed for optical failure monitoring and DDoS attack detection using a combination of DPI and deep learning techniques. The system, specifically designed for DPU execution, is structured into two use cases, optical failure monitoring and DDoS detection. Each use case consists of two modules that utilize DPI and deep learning, as shown in Figure 3. Figure 3 illustrates the workflows of our proposed system model. This setup uses Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) using DOCS SDK API (DOCA flow) to inspect packets in real-time, at line rates, for potential threats in high-speed optical networks. The optical use case utilized DPI and deep learning for optical failure monitoring. Security use case demonstrates for detection of DDoS attacks utilizing DPI and deep learning. DPI Module handles packet inspection at wire speed, identifying optical parameters for failure detection and tracing suspicious DDoS packets based on predefined threat signatures and thresholds. Only packets flagged by the DPI are forwarded to the CNN model for further analysis. Once flagged by DPI, packets are processed by CNN models on the DPU/GPU, which perform a detailed investigation for optical failure or DDoS attack detection. The combination of DPI for real-time filtering and CNN for selective deeper analysis ensures that packet processing at line rates (up to 100 Gbps) is not compromised, allowing the network to operate efficiently without latency issues. This approach ensures that the AI models, while powerful for detecting complex attack patterns, do not bottleneck network traffic, as they only analyze a small fraction of the total packet flow.

A. Optical Monitoring Using DPI

Traditionally, optical monitoring data are retrieved from the optical components, processed by the CPU of the host system, encapsulated in network packets, and delivered to remote nodes or telemetry collectors. Here, those network packets are first retrieved from the network interface, then processed by the host CPU and stored in external time-series databases where

Fig. 2. Proposed Edge Network Architecture.

AI processing can take place. The introduction of DPU with embedded GPU and coherent transceivers has the potential to significantly improve the efficiency of this procedure. Indeed, optical monitoring data can be locally retrieved by the DPU from the plugged transceiver. Then, hardware-offloaded DPI can be used to extract packet network information avoiding the interaction with the CPU of the host system. Finally, the local GPU can directly perform AI processing, overall guaranteeing fast reaction time and forecasting capabilities.

In this work, a specific innovative DPI component has been developed for extracting optical monitoring data from custom-built UDP packets containing payload information about selected monitoring parameters, such as BER and power levels of optical fiber devices. Then, the hardware-accelerated DPI system continuously inspects these payloads, comparing against predefined thresholds directly configured within the DPU pipes. If the monitored parameters exceed these thresholds, indicating a potential failure, the system is able to react efficiently, performing further elaborations (e.g., exploiting the embedded GPU, see next subsection) and/or sending automated warning/alarm messages possibly leading to traffic reroute even before the link fails. This proactive approach ensures continuous network reliability and operational efficiency also in case of soft-failures.

B. Optical Failure Monitoring Using Deep Learning

To enhance live detection capabilities, the results of the DPI inspections for optical monitoring are fed into the deep learning models. For optical monitoring, the metrics extracted from DPI, such as BER and power levels, are provided as input features to the CNN. This enables the CNN to make real-time predictions about potential optical failures based on the latest network conditions. We use standard CNNs to analyze data collected from optical networks. The CNN model is trained to detect both gradual and sudden degradations of critical parameters (e.g. pre-FEC BER and power levels), which are indicative of potential failures

Fig. 3. Proposed System Model and Components

in the optical fiber network. The system utilizes both historical data and latest monitoring metrics to predict soft-failures and the remaining useful life (RUL) of the optical components. By forecasting potential failures, the system can trigger preventive recovery and maintenance actions before actual failures occur, thus enhancing network reliability and minimizing downtime.

C. DDoS Detection Using DPI

Conventional approaches use distinct systems for cybersecurity, leading to integration challenges and higher latency. Traditional monitoring tools often lack the ability to process data in real-time, which is a key requirement for prompt detection and response. Ensuring high accuracy in detecting anomalies requires significant computational resources, which can be a bottleneck in high-speed networks. Conventional DDoS detection systems are often reactive, addressing issues only after they have occurred, leading to potential network downtime and reduced reliability. To address these challenges, we present an integrated system that leverages DPI combined with deep learning models, specifically CNNs, running on DPUs with embedded GPUs. The use of DPUs with embedded GPUs allows for the real-time processing of vast amounts of data, ensuring timely detection and response. The DPU-based DPI system is designed and implemented to continuously monitor incoming network traffic to

detect potential DDoS attacks.

The system, shown in Figure 4, begins by checking if the traffic rate exceeds predefined thresholds, dropping or rate-limiting packets to mitigate immediate threats. Packets that pass this initial threshold check are sent to the Stateful Flow Tracking (SFT) module, which maintains stateful information about network flows, enabling the recognition and tracking of individual flow behaviors over time. The DPI engine inspects packet payloads in detail, comparing attributes against a database of known DDoS attack signatures. If a match is found, the system drops the packet and logs the attack information. This layered approach ensures comprehensive protection against DDoS attacks, leveraging both threshold-based and signature-based detection mechanisms.

C.1. Packet Monitoring and Threshold Detection

The DPI system continuously monitors incoming network traffic to detect potential DDoS attacks. When the traffic rate exceeds predefined thresholds, packets are either dropped or rate-limited to mitigate the immediate threat. This initial step ensures that the system can handle surges in traffic volume without overwhelming the network infrastructure.

C.2. Stateful Flow Tracking (SFT)

Packets that pass the initial threshold checks are sent to the Stateful Flow Tracking (SFT) module using the `sft_process_packet()` function. SFT maintains stateful information about network flows, enabling the system to recognize and track the behavior of individual flows over time.

If a packet is not marked with a zone ID by the hardware, the SFT is informed about the packet's zone using the `sft_process_packet_with_zone()` function. For packets not marked with a flow ID, a new flow is created using the `sft_activate()` function, followed by invoking `doca_dpi_flow_create()` if a new flow ID is assigned.

C.3. DPI Processing and Signature Matching

Packets are then enqueued for DPI processing using the `doca_dpi_enqueue()` function. The DPI engine inspects the packet payloads in detail, extracting attributes such as source and destination addresses, protocol information, and payload content. The extracted attributes are compared against a database of predefined signatures representing known DDoS attack patterns.

The results of the DPI processing are dequeued using the `doca_dpi_dequeue()` function. If a match is found, the system checks if it corresponds to a DDoS signature. If so, the packet is dropped. Otherwise, match statistics are printed, and the flow is offloaded to the host for further processing. The detected threat information is retrieved using `doca_dpi_signature_get()`, and the flow is terminated using `doca_dpi_flow_destroy()`.

D. DDoS Detection Using Deep Learning

In traditional network security approaches, Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) is commonly implemented on edge devices using the CPU. This setup can introduce significant performance bottlenecks, particularly when handling high volumes of network traffic. The CPU, responsible for both DPI operations and other system tasks, can become overloaded, leading to slower processing speeds and reduced efficiency. Furthermore, integrating deep learning models for real-time analysis alongside DPI is challenging with conventional CPU-based systems due to their high computational demands and limited parallel processing

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the DPI Packet Processing for Optical Monitoring and DDoS detection and integration with Deep Learning

capabilities. This limitation hampers the ability to perform simultaneous DPI and deep learning analyses, thereby affecting the responsiveness and accuracy of DDoS attack detection.

To address these challenges and enhance the real-time detection of DDoS attacks, we integrate DPI results with deep learning models. DPI provides critical packet attributes and detected signatures, which are continuously updated and fed into a CNN. This dynamic integration allows the CNN to refine its understanding of both normal and malicious traffic patterns, thereby improving its accuracy in real-time DDoS attack detection. By leveraging DPI inspection outcomes, the system adopts a more adaptive and responsive approach to network security and monitoring.

We utilize CNNs to analyze network traffic data and detect patterns indicative of DDoS attacks. The CNN model is trained on features such as packet rate, size, and distribution to differentiate between normal and malicious traffic. This continuous learning process enables the CNN-based detection system to identify and respond to emerging DDoS threats in real time. The integration of deep learning with DPI inspection results provides a robust defense mechanism, enhancing network security and resilience against sophisticated DDoS attacks.

6. IMPLEMENTATION

In this section, we report on the implementation of the proposed system model based on the aforementioned four main components. The implementation of optical failure monitoring and DDoS attack detection using DPI and deep learning involves several steps, as outlined in Algorithm 1, Algorithm 2 and Al-

gorithm 3. These algorithms detail the process of monitoring incoming traffic, processing packets, and taking action based on detected optical transmission metrics or detected DDoS attack signatures, respectively, including deep learning classification where applicable.

A. Fiber Optical network Monitoring using DPI

We employ DPI to monitor Bit Error Rate (BER) and fiber power in optical networks, enabling proactive maintenance and failure prediction. In BlueField-2 with DOCA, DPI operations are tightly integrated with hardware offload mechanisms to ensure efficient and high-performance packet processing. We leverage specialized hardware components, such as BlueField-2 SmartNICs, to offload DPI tasks from the host CPU. These SmartNICs are equipped with dedicated processing units optimized for packet inspection and analysis, allowing for parallelized and accelerated DPI operations.

When an incoming packet arrives at the SmartNIC, it undergoes deep inspection to extract key attributes, including BER and fiber power values embedded in the payload. After identifying the flow and ensuring it meets certain criteria, such as not exceeding predefined rate thresholds, packets are enqueued for DPI processing. Upon successful processing of the packet by the DPI engine, the result is dequeued for further analysis. If a match is found during DPI processing, it prints and counts match statistics related to the detected metrics. If the BER and fiber power values exceed predefined thresholds, indicating potential link failure, a rerouting request is sent to the edge node to reroute traffic before a failure occurs. Otherwise, the flow is hardware offloaded to the host for further processing. Informa-

Fig. 5. Network testbed.

tion about the detected metrics is retrieved from the DPI engine for logging or further action. Once the packet processing is complete, the flow is terminated. These statistics about the packet processing, DPI results, and flow termination are retrieved for deep learning training.

This inspection is performed at wire speed, ensuring minimal latency and maximum throughput. The DPI engine compares the extracted packet attributes against a database of predefined signatures representing known thresholds and patterns for BER and fiber power. DPI maintains stateful flow tracking information to contextualize packet inspection results. By associating packets with specific network connections or flows, DPI can detect anomalous behavior and identify patterns indicative of potential failures. Upon detecting a match between packet attributes and a threshold in the database, DPI can trigger enforcement actions to mitigate the risk. These actions include sending rerouting requests, packet dropping, rate limiting, and redirection towards another port, depending on the severity and nature of the detected metrics.

DPI operations are seamlessly integrated into the broader DOCA framework, allowing for centralized management and orchestration of network performance and security policies. DOCA provides a unified interface for configuring DPI settings, monitoring traffic patterns, and responding to events in real-time. To stay current with network conditions, the DPI regularly updates its signature database. These updates are automatically distributed and applied across BlueField-2 SmartNICs, ensuring that the network remains optimized and protected against evolving risks. DPI signature creation involves a combination of manual analysis, network intelligence gathering, and automated tooling provided by DOCA API.

B. Implementation of Optical Monitoring using Deep Learning Model

The presence of DPUs equipped with coherent transceivers allows for efficient monitoring and correlation capabilities to be directly integrated into the network card. The received packet and optical data can be processed locally, utilizing high-performance GPU resources. For instance, the in-band telemetry can provide detailed information about the latency performance of each packet. This information can be analysed by embedded P4/DOCA libraries using AI-based algorithms, which are more effective than traditional threshold-based mechanisms. Unlike these mechanisms, which simply send telemetry data to remote management systems, the AI-based algorithms can achieve better results. In addition, the DPU has the ability to process opti-

cal parameters received by the local transceivers on-site. As a demonstration of its feasibility, we present the empirical verification of an artificial intelligence (AI) algorithm initially developed for identifying minor malfunctions, which is controlled by a centralised Software-Defined Networking (SDN) Controller [35]. In this case, the algorithm is being used to evaluate local conditions within the DPU. Figure 5 depicts the network testbed under consideration. Two DELL PowerEdge Servers are outfitted with NVIDIA Bluefield2 DPUs that include integrated Graphics Processing Units (GPUs). Due to the lack of support for coherent transceivers in these DPUs, we depend on Edgecore switches that are equipped with 400ZR+ coherent transceivers. Nevertheless, the DPU manages the transceivers using a Rest interface rather than relying on an SDN Controller. This allows the transceivers to be controlled as if they were physically integrated into the DPU. Subsequently, the two transceivers are joined by three optically amplified spans, each spanning a distance of 80 km.

The implementation of optical failure monitoring using deep learning involves collecting optical parameters, training a deep learning model offline using CSV files, and deploying the model for real-time predictions, as detailed in Algorithm 2. This algorithm describes the process of data collection, offline training, real-time prediction, and preventive actions.

Initially, data is collected from optical devices, including Bit Error Rate (BER) values and power levels, and stored in CSV files for offline training. The collected data is preprocessed to prepare it for training, which includes normalization and handling missing values. The preprocessed data is then used to train a CNN model offline. The CNN architecture, as described in Table 1, is used for this purpose. The training process involves splitting the data into training and validation sets, defining the CNN architecture, and tuning hyperparameters. The model is trained using five datasets of optical failure, ensuring a robust understanding of various failure scenarios. Once the model is trained, it is saved for deployment in the production stage.

In real-time, the trained CNN model is deployed, and BER and power level data are collected from optical devices. The deployed CNN model uses this real-time data to predict potential failures by comparing current metrics against learned patterns of normal operation and failure scenarios. The system maintains a feedback loop where detected anomalies and predictions are validated against actual outcomes. This feedback is used to periodically retrain and fine-tune the CNN model using new data collected and stored in CSV files. By updating the training dataset with confirmed failures and normal operation data,

Algorithm 1. DPI Packet Processing for BER and Fiber Power Monitoring with Reroute Request

Require: Incoming packet
Ensure: Processing results, statistics, and reroute requests if thresholds are exceeded
 Monitor incoming traffic to identify potential data of interest
 if Incoming traffic rate exceeds predefined threshold **then**
 Drop or rate-limit incoming packets
 Return
 Send packet to Stateful Flow Tracking (SFT) for processing with `sft_process_packet()`
 if Hardware recognizes the flow **then**
 if Packet is not marked with zone ID by HW **then**
 Inform SFT about zone of packet with `sft_process_packet_with_zone()`
 if Packet is not marked with flow ID by HW or SW **then**
 Create new flow with `sft_activate()`
 if New flow ID is assigned by SFT **then**
 Invoke `doca_dpi_flow_create()` before enqueueing packet
 Enforce rate limits for incoming packets
 if Rate limits exceeded **then**
 Drop or rate-limit incoming packets
 Return
 Enqueue packet for DPI processing with `doca_dpi_enqueue()`
 if Packet is accepted by DPI for processing **then**
 Dequeue result with `doca_dpi_dequeue()`
 if Match is found **then**
 if Matched with BER and Fiber Power signature **then**
 Extract BER and Fiber Power values
 Print and count match statistics
 Store BER and Fiber Power data for further analysis
 if BER or Fiber Power is different from predefined thresholds **then**
 Send reroute the request to the edge node
 Return
 Offload flow to host
 Retrieve match from DPI engine with `doca_dpi_signature_get()`
 Terminate flow with `doca_dpi_flow_destroy()`
 Retrieve additional statistics with `doca_dpi_stat_get()`

the model's accuracy improves over time. Upon predicting a potential failure, the system triggers preventive actions, such as rerouting traffic or scheduling maintenance, to avoid downtime.

The CNN model and training process involve several steps. Data preprocessing includes loading data from CSV files, normalizing it to ensure all features have a similar scale, and handling missing values by either imputing them or discarding incomplete records. The model architecture, as outlined in Table 1, consists of an input layer that accepts BER and power level data, convolutional layers to extract features from the input data, pooling layers to reduce the dimensionality of the feature maps, fully connected layers to combine features to predict potential failures, and an output layer that produces the final prediction (failure or no failure). The training process involves splitting the data into training and validation sets, defining the CNN architecture, and compiling the model with an appropriate loss function and optimizer. The model is then trained using the training set and validated using the validation set, with hyperparameters

Algorithm 2. Optical Failure Monitoring using Deep Learning

Require: Collected BER and power level data in CSV files
Ensure: Real-time predictions and preventive actions
 Collect and store BER and power level data in CSV files
 Preprocess the collected data (normalization, handling missing values)
 Train CNN model offline using preprocessed data and the architecture in Table 1
 Save the trained CNN model
 Deploy the trained CNN model to production
 Collect real-time BER and power level data from optical devices
 Use the CNN model to predict potential failures
 if Potential failure predicted **then**
 Trigger preventive actions (rerouting traffic, scheduling maintenance)
 Maintain feedback loop to validate predictions and update training dataset
 Periodically retrain and fine-tune the CNN model using new data

tuned to optimize performance.

C. Implementation of DDoS attack detection using DPI

We employ DPI to detect and block DDoS traffic effectively. In BlueField-2 with DOCA, DPI (Deep Packet Inspection) operations are tightly integrated with hardware offload mechanisms to ensure efficient and high-performance packet processing. Here's how DPI works and its connection with hardware offload:

We leverage specialized hardware components, such as BlueField-2 SmartNIC, to offload DPI tasks from the host CPU. These SmartNICs are equipped with dedicated processing units optimized for packet inspection and analysis, allowing for parallelized and accelerated DPI operations. When an incoming packet arrives at the SmartNIC, it undergoes deep inspection to extract key attributes such as source and destination addresses, protocol information, and payload content. After identifying the flow and ensuring it meets certain criteria, such as not exceeding predefined rate thresholds, packets are enqueued for DPI processing. Upon successful processing of the packet by the DPI engine, the result is dequeued for further analysis. If a match is found during DPI processing, it prints and counts match statistics related to the detected threat. If the match corresponds to a known DDoS signature, the packet is dropped. Otherwise, the flow is hardware offloaded to the host for further processing. Information about the detected threat is retrieved from the DPI engine for logging or further action. Once the packet processing is complete, the flow is terminated. These statistics about the packet processing, DPI results, and flow termination are retrieved for deep learning training. This inspection is performed at wire speed, ensuring minimal latency and maximum throughput. The DPI engine compares the extracted packet attributes against a database of predefined signatures representing known threats and attack patterns. These signatures are meticulously crafted based on the characteristics of common DDoS attack patterns and we can also utilize these for other malicious activities detection. DPI maintains stateful flow tracking information to contextualize packet inspection results. By associating packets with specific network connections or flows, DPI can detect anomalous behavior and identify patterns indicative of security threats. Upon detecting a match between packet attributes and a

Algorithm 3. DPI Packet Processing with Hardware offload DDoS Signature Matching

```

Require: Incoming packet
Ensure: Processing results and statistics
Monitor incoming traffic to identify potential DDoS attacks
if Incoming traffic rate exceeds predefined threshold then
  Drop or rate-limit incoming packets
Return
Send packet to Stateful Flow Tracking (SFT) for processing
with sft_process_packet()
if Hardware recognizes the flow then
  if Packet is not marked with zone ID by HW then
    Inform SFT about zone of packet with
sft_process_packet_with_zone()
  if Packet is not marked with flow ID by HW or SW then
    Create new flow with sft_activate()
  if New flow ID is assigned by SFT then
    Invoke doca_dpi_flow_create() before enqueue-
ing packet
Enforce rate limits for incoming packets
if Rate limits exceeded then
  Drop or rate-limit incoming packets
Return
Enqueue packet for DPI processing with
doca_dpi_enqueue()
if Packet is accepted by DPI for processing then
  Dequeue result with doca_dpi_dequeue()
  if Match is found then
    if Matched with DDoS signature then
      Drop packet
    else
      Print and count match statistics
      Offload flow to host
Retrieve match from DPI engine with
doca_dpi_signature_get()
Terminate flow with doca_dpi_flow_destroy()
Retrieve additional statistics with doca_dpi_stat_get()

```

signature in the database, DPI can trigger enforcement actions to mitigate the threat. These actions include packet dropping, rate limiting, and redirection toward another port, depending on the severity and nature of the detected threat. DPI operations are seamlessly integrated into the broader DOCA framework, allowing for centralized management and orchestration of network security policies. DOCA provides a unified interface for configuring DPI settings, monitoring traffic patterns, and responding to security events in real-time. To stay current with emerging threats and vulnerabilities, Suricata-based DPI regularly updates its signature database. These updates are automatically distributed and applied across BlueField-2 SmartNICs, ensuring that the network remains protected against evolving security risks. DPI signature creation involves a combination of manual analysis, threat intelligence gathering, and automated tooling provided by DOCA API.

D. Implementation of DDoS attack detection using Deep learning Model

The presence of hardware-accelerated security functions within DPUs provides native embedded security to edge infrastructures. A novel framework for live traffic analysis and intrusion detection on the DPU is here presented. It relies on a combi-

nation of DPDK libraries, DOCA library that provides Regular Expression (RegEx) pattern matching to DOCA applications for Deep Packet Inspection (DPI), and the Suricata intrusion detection system. The framework leverages hardware acceleration to perform DPI and deep learning-based intrusion detection. This enables the offloading of Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) detection tasks to the DPU. Initially, the DPU receives incoming traffic and performs RegEx operations to detect malicious traffic. If the traffic is benign, it is forwarded to the edge CPU for further processing; otherwise, the DPU drops malicious traffic. The framework relies on a deep learning-based CNN model to detect DDoS attacks in real-time. The model was trained and tested using the CICDDOS2019 and optical datasets. We employ the CNN model, whose architecture is described in Table 1 uses a sequence of layers to extract features and make classifications. The architecture is optimized to handle packets of length 1512 bytes, which are commonly used packet sizes in network traffic analysis. At the core of the CNN architecture are convolutional layers, which play a crucial role in capturing local patterns within the input data. Learnable filters are used in these layers to extract features that distinguish between normal and malicious traffic. By employing three convolutional layers, the network model can automatically learn hierarchical features, progressively capturing more abstract representations of the data. Activation functions, Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) and Leaky ReLU, introduce non-linearity to the model, enabling it to learn complex relationships between 5G network traffic features.

ReLU is defined as:

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (1)$$

Leaky ReLU, which allows a small, non-zero gradient when the input is negative, is defined as:

$$\text{Leaky ReLU}(x, \alpha) = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ \alpha x & \text{if } x < 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The CNN model is optimized using a categorical cross-entropy loss function, which is well-suited for multi-class classification tasks. Mathematically expression for the cross-entropy loss is:

$$\text{Loss} = - \sum_i \text{True Class}_i \cdot \log(\text{Predicted}_i) \quad (3)$$

where True Class_i represents the true label of the i -th class, and Predicted_i represents the predicted probability of the i -th class.

D.1. Model Training

We trained the CNN model on the preprocessed network traffic data using TensorFlow Lite on the Nvidia DPU. This allowed us to leverage the DPU's hardware acceleration capabilities to achieve faster training times and lower computational costs. We used a transfer learning approach to reduce the complexity of the proposed CNN algorithm. Then we evaluated and fine-tuned the model on the CICDDOS2019 dataset using TensorFlow Lite on the Nvidia DPU. We used a simple architecture for the CNN model with two convolutional layers, followed by a fully connected layer. The convolutional layers used a kernel size of 3 and a stride of 1. The fully connected layer had 128 neurons. Our model is trained using the Adam optimizer and the cross-entropy loss function. We trained the models for 100 epochs with a batch size of 64. The choice of these hyperparameters

Table 1. CNN Model Architecture

Layers	Filters	Kernel Size	Activation Function
Convolutional	32	3×3	ReLU
Max Pooling	-	2×2	-
Convolutional	64	3×3	ReLU
Max Pooling	-	2×2	-
Convolutional	128	3×3	ReLU
Flatten	-	-	-
Fully Connected	128	-	ReLU
Fully Connected	64	-	ReLU
Output	1	-	Sigmoid

(epochs and batch size) is optimized through hyperparameter tuning techniques, potentially leading to better performance. The model is trained on the training data using the selected hyperparameters. The loss function is optimized using the Adam optimizer. During the training process, we monitored various performance metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, false positive rate (FPR), and false negative rate (FNR). These metrics provide a comprehensive evaluation of the models' performance in detecting DDoS attacks. The accuracy metric measures the overall correctness of the model predictions, while precision represents the proportion of true positive predictions out of all positive predictions made by the model. Recall, also known as sensitivity, measures the proportion of true positive predictions out of all actual positive instances in the dataset. F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balance between the two metrics.

E. Offline Training

For the detection of DDoS attacks, a second CNN is trained using the CICDDoS2019 dataset, a widely-used dataset for detecting DDoS attacks. This dataset includes labeled network traffic that contains both normal and malicious traffic patterns. The CICDDoS2019 dataset is used to train the DDoS detection model. This dataset contains a large number of labeled network traffic flows, each indicating whether it is normal traffic or part of a DDoS attack. Feature Extraction: Features such as packet rate, packet size, source and destination IPs, and protocol types are extracted from the network traffic. These features are critical for distinguishing between normal and malicious traffic. Similarly to the optical monitoring model, a CNN is used to detect DDoS attacks. The model is designed to process time-series network traffic data and identify patterns associated with attack behavior. The CNN is trained using supervised learning, with labeled traffic data indicating normal or DDoS attacks. The model learns to identify the characteristics of DDoS attacks such as high packet rates, abnormal flow behavior, and malicious signatures. A validation set is used to monitor the performance of the model during training, ensuring that the CNN does not overfit the training data and performs well on unseen traffic. Hyperparameters, including the number of convolutional layers, learning rate, and activation functions, are tuned to achieve the

best performance. Regularization techniques are used to prevent overfitting. Once trained, this CNN is deployed on the DPU, where it works in conjunction with Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) to analyze live network traffic for potential DDoS attacks. The model continuously monitors traffic patterns, adapting to new attack vectors as it processes data in real-time.

F. Deployment and Real-Time Inference

After offline training, the models are deployed on DPUs with embedded GPUs for real-time inference. The DPI system extracts relevant features from live network traffic (optical data for the optical monitoring model and network packet data for the DDoS detection model). The CNNs then process these features, providing real-time predictions of potential optical failures and DDoS attacks. This offline training process ensures that both models are well-prepared to handle real-time challenges in optical failure detection and DDoS attack mitigation, contributing to the overall security and reliability of the network.

During the training process, we monitored various performance metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, false positive rate (FPR), and false negative rate (FNR). These metrics provide a comprehensive evaluation of the models' performance in detecting DDoS attacks.

$$\text{Accuracy (ACC)} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Precision (P)} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Recall (R)} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{F1 Score (F1)} = 2 \times \frac{P \times R}{P + R} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{False Positive Rate (FPR)} = \frac{FP}{FP + TN} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{False Negative Rate (FNR)} = \frac{FN}{FN + TP} \quad (9)$$

7. RESULTS

This section presents a performance analysis of optical failure monitoring and DDoS attack detection, including inference times, accuracy metrics, and confusion matrices for optical failure monitoring and DDoS attack detection.

In this section, we compare inference time for DDoS attack detection using the DPI custom dataset and the CICDDoS2019 dataset. Also we report on the analysis of the deep learning model in terms of accuracy, recall, F1 score, and precision. Then, a comparison of the average inference time of the DPU solution and the DPU with an embedded GPU solution is provided. We also compare accuracy with DPI and without DPI for both optical fiber monitoring and DDoS attack detection.

Figure 6 shows the inference time comparison for optical failure monitoring with and without DPI. Data was collected from five different datasets representing various network environments. The results indicate that the DPI-based solution has a significantly lower inference time due to its real-time packet inspection capabilities, which streamline the process of identifying potential optical failures. Each dataset consists of 30 optical parameters derived from a source [35]. These parameters simulate a single received signal event. The inference times represent the

duration taken to analyze the packet data and predict potential optical failures. The DPI system inspects UDP packets carrying payload information about Pre-FEC BER and power levels from optical devices. These values are processed in real-time to identify any threshold breaches that indicate potential optical failures. The processed BER values and power levels are passed to the CNN model. The CNN model compares the real-time data against learned patterns to predict potential failures. With DPI, the average inference time across all datasets is around 0.54 ms. In the absence of DPI, the system directly processes packet attributes for anomaly detection without the initial inspection and preprocessing by DPI. The CNN model analyzes the data to predict potential failures. Without DPI, the average inference time across all datasets is around 2.49 ms. This demonstrates that utilizing DPI for optical failure monitoring significantly reduces the inference time, making it more efficient for real-time anomaly detection.

Figure 7 compares the inference times for DDoS attack detection using the DPI custom dataset and the CICDDoS2019 dataset. The DPI-based solution again shows reduced inference times, highlighting its efficiency in processing network traffic and more swiftly detecting DDoS attacks. The DPI system monitors incoming network traffic and inspects packet attributes such as source, destination, protocol, and payload. DPI checks these attributes against known DDoS attack signatures to identify potential threats. The results from DPI are passed to a deep learning model. With DPI, the average inference time for the DPI custom dataset is around 0.74 ms, and for the CICDDoS2019 dataset is around 0.84 ms. Without DPI, the system processes incoming network traffic for anomaly detection without the initial inspection and signature matching by DPI. The CNN model analyzes the data to identify DDoS attack patterns. Without DPI, the average inference time for the DPI custom dataset is around 2.31 ms, and for the CICDDoS2019 dataset is around 2.50 ms. This shows that the inference time for DDoS attack detection is significantly reduced when DPI is used, highlighting the efficiency of DPI in pre-processing and filtering relevant data before deep learning models analyze it.

Rapid processing enables the development of innovative decentralised control plane capabilities, allowing each node to receive telemetry data from many data plane nodes without being hindered by scalability problems. We applied the CNN model for a directed mitigation approach to achieve this goal. To compare the effectiveness of our proposed approach for both use cases, we also implemented and tested two existing detection methods: DIDDOS [36] and LUCID [37] for the security use case. These methods were selected based on previous research and their suitability for similar application environments. The performance of these deep learning-based methods (optical monitoring and DDoS detection) was assessed using traditional classification metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Accuracy represents the proportion of flow records that were correctly classified, while precision measures the proportion of accurately recognized abnormal IP flows among all samples identified as unusual. Recall estimates the proportion of correctly identified anomalous flows, and the F1 score represents the harmonic mean between true-positive rate (i.e., malicious flows classified as abnormal) and precision. The performance analysis presented in this section focuses on two different test scenarios that use the public CICDDoS2019 dataset and the custom dataset to evaluate the effectiveness of anomaly detection approaches. In the first experiment, we utilized simulated IP flows sourced from the CICDDoS2019 dataset. This dataset com-

prises 87 IP flow features, from which we selected 78 features by excluding specific dimensions to avoid data bias. The dataset includes 12 types of DDoS attacks for training and six for testing.

Fig. 6. Inference Time for optical monitoring use case.

Fig. 7. Inference Time for DDoS attack use case.

Figure 8 shows the evaluation results of these deep learning models of CNN for DDoS attack detection and fiber optical monitoring. The evaluation metrics used are accuracy, recall, and F1-score. Optical monitoring use case achieves an accuracy of 99.45%, recall of 99.43%, F1-score of 99.66%, FPR of 99.57%, and FNR of 0.46%. The CNN model for the security use case achieves an accuracy of 99.41%, recall of 99.55%, F1-score of 99.64%, FPR of 98.78%, and FNR of 0.44%. With these evaluation results, we have a minimum average inference time shown in Figure 9. Figure 10 illustrates the changes in DDoS detection accuracy over time with and without the integration of DPI results. Using standalone deep learning models, it shows high accuracy levels for the DDoS detection system. The accuracy is well above 99%, reflecting strong performance. After DPI Integration: Indicates that the accuracy remains consistently high or improves with the integration of DPI results. The incorporation of real-time DPI data enhances the system's ability to detect and mitigate DDoS attacks, maintaining or even improving high accuracy levels. This plot demonstrates that the integration of DPI with deep learning continues to support exceptional accuracy in DDoS detection, reinforcing the effectiveness of this combined approach.

Fig. 8. Fiber Optical Monitoring and DDoS Attack Evaluation Results Using DPU with Embedded GPU.

Fig. 9. Average Monitoring Inference Time with DPU(GPU) DPU(CPU).

Figure 11 shows the accuracy of optical failure monitoring over time with and without DPI integration. Before DPI Integration: Reflects high accuracy levels with conventional methods, exceeding 99% for optical monitoring. Demonstrates that the accuracy remains high or improves with DPI integration. This indicates that combining DPI metrics with deep learning enhances the system’s ability to monitor and predict optical failures effectively. This plot highlights the benefits of integrating DPI with deep learning for optical monitoring, showing that the combined approach maintains or enhances high accuracy levels.

Table 2. Evaluation results of the Security use-case using CNN models for DDoS attack detection and Monitoring use-case

Model	Accuracy	Recall	F1-Score	FPR	FNR
Monitoring	0.9945	0.9943	0.9966	0.9957	0.0056
Security	0.9941	0.9955	0.9964	0.9878	0.0044

Table 2 presents the performance metrics for two specific use cases: optical monitoring and security. The Monitoring use case achieved an accuracy of 0.9945, while the security use case reached 0.9941. Recall for the Monitoring use case is 0.9943, and

Fig. 10. DDoS Detection Accuracy Over Time.

Fig. 11. Optical Failure Monitoring Accuracy Over Time.

for the security use case, it is 0.9955. F1-score for monitoring is slightly higher at 0.9966, compared to 0.9964 for Security. Monitoring has an FPR of 0.9957, while the Security use case has a lower FPR of 0.9878. FNR is 0.0056 for Monitoring and 0.0044 for Security, indicating a low rate of false negatives in both instances. We can see in Figure 12 that the CNN correctly classified 234933 instances of normal traffic as normal (99.43% True Negatives) and 239530 instances of malicious traffic as malicious (99.56% True Positives). However, it incorrectly classified 3622 instances of normal traffic as malicious (0.57% False Positives) and 33 instances of malicious traffic as normal (0.44% False Negatives). We also see in Figure 12 optical monitoring confusion matrix that correctly classified 235640 instances as true positive and 239534 as True negative. However, it incorrectly classified 2915 instances as False Positive (0.43% False Positives) and 29 instances of False Negative as usual (0.44% False Negatives). This confusion matrix provides us with valuable information about our CNN Models.

Figure 13 demonstrates the effectiveness of DPI in handling a large-scale UDP DDoS attack. According to the figure, DPI successfully processed 58,892 packets of the attack, which is a significant achievement. This showcases the power of DPI in identifying and mitigating malicious traffic in real-time. By examining the content of each packet, DPI can distinguish be-

Fig. 12. Confusion matrix of CNN-based DDoS attack detection and optical monitoring

tween legitimate and harmful traffic, allowing it to selectively block packets associated with an attack while allowing legitimate traffic to pass through unimpeded. This figure highlights the importance of DPI in defending against DDoS attacks, which remain a significant threat to network security and availability. This indicates that the proposed system can efficiently handle

```

[08:11:13:382424][DOCA][INF][DWRKR:830]: ..... DPI STATISTICS .....
[08:11:13:382497][DOCA][INF][DWRKR:831]: Packets scanned by SSSA DPI:58892
[08:11:13:382518][DOCA][INF][DWRKR:832]: Matched signatures:58892
[08:11:13:382535][DOCA][INF][DWRKR:833]: TCP matches:0
[08:11:13:382553][DOCA][INF][DWRKR:834]: UDP matches:58892
[08:11:13:382570][DOCA][INF][DWRKR:835]: HTTP matches:0
[08:11:13:382587][DOCA][INF][DWRKR:836]: SSL matches:0
[08:11:13:382604][DOCA][INF][DWRKR:837]: Miscellaneous L4:0, L7:0
[08:11:15:599303][DOCA][ERR][OFRLS:410]: query failed, error=invalid flow handle
[08:11:15:599369][DOCA][ERR][OFRLS:410]: query failed, error=invalid flow handle

```

Fig. 13. Bluefield DPU DPI statistics

large volumes of attack traffic without experiencing significant strain on its resources. The high processing speed and low utilization can be attributed to advanced hardware and software technologies, such as DPDK, Regex-based DPI, and deep learning algorithms. This figure demonstrates the system's ability to effectively mitigate cyber attacks, which is critical for ensuring the availability and security of network resources.

Table 3. Comparison of Models in terms of CPU Load, Latency, Throughput, and F1 Score for Security Use Case

Platforms	CPU Load (%)	Latency (ms)	Throughput (Gbps)
Lucid-DDoS Server [37]	92.6	35	10.5
Security Server	68.0	12.85	20.0
Monitoring Server	70.8	12.7	21.8
Security DPU	26.3	5.5	99.36
Monitoring inside DPU	26.7	5.5	99.8

Table 3 shows that the CPU load significantly varies depending on the platform. The LUCID-DDoS CNN-based IDS inside the server CPU showed a high CPU load of 92.6%, indicating that it consumes most of the CPU's processing power. In contrast, the LUCID-DDoS CNN-based IDS implementation inside DPU is impossible due to the ARM-based processor. Moreover, the proposed CNN-based models significantly improved CPU load compared to LUCID-DDoS CNN-based IDS, mainly when deployed inside DPU. Table 3 also shows that optical monitoring and DDoS attack detection CPU load is lower on the DPU than

on the server CPU. The DPU is a more efficient platform for running CNN models. The proposed optical failure monitoring model and DDoS detection model inside DPU showed an extremely low CPU load of up to 26.3%, which is much more efficient than the other state-of-the-art methods.

8. DISCUSSION

In this section, we discuss the rationale behind our choice of machine learning models and the advantages of employing DPUs with embedded GPUs at edge level over traditional P4-based solutions in optical networks. Edge-based monitoring enables real-time anomaly detection and reduces latency, which is critical for time-sensitive security applications. We analyze the economic and performance advantages of deploying DPUs with embedded GPUs compared to P4-based in-network computing solutions. We consider factors such as price, throughput, operational costs, AI integration, scalability, and hardware limitations. DPUs with embedded GPUs present a compelling solution for optical networks, especially at the edge, by directly providing high computational power and AI processing within the network infrastructure.

A. Edge Network Instead of Centralized Monitoring

Optical edge environments, particularly those in critical infrastructure such as 5G networks, require ultra-low latency for real-time decision-making. By offloading optical monitoring to the edge, we minimize the delay caused by transmitting data to centralized locations for analysis. For real-time and time-sensitive applications, such as detecting failures in optical links, immediate responses are necessary to maintain service quality and prevent further network issues. It also helps localized decision-making, which is increasingly important as networks scale. Edge-based monitoring can rapidly detect and address problems close to the source, preventing bottlenecks or failures from propagating through the network.

B. Rationale for Choosing CNNs

We opted for CNNs due to their proven capability to effectively extract spatial features from data, which is crucial for detecting anomalies in optical networks. Despite the input data not being in typical grid-like formats, CNNs have demonstrated superior performance in tasks requiring feature extraction, particularly in security use cases. We compared the features, metrics, and performance of MLP and CNN models in Table 4, and we presented performance metrics with a specifically use case-based comparison in Table 5. This revealed that CNNs outperformed MLPs in accuracy and handling complex patterns inherent in security-related data. The ability of CNNs to identify subtle anomalies is critical for the timely detection of network attacks and operational failures. Moreover, CNNs serve as a unified model that can be employed across security and optical data monitoring tasks, maintaining consistency and reducing the complexity of managing multiple models. Given these advantages, CNNs were the optimal choice for our implementation.

The comparison shows that while MLPs are effective for general tasks, CNNs significantly outperform them in feature extraction, especially for spatial data relevant to our application. This reinforces our decision to use CNNs for security and optical data monitoring tasks, where the complexity of data and the need for accurate anomaly detection are paramount.

Table 4. Comparison of MLP and CNN

Feature	Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)[38]	Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)
Architecture	Fully connected layers	Convolutional layers with pooling
Feature Extraction	Limited; relies on input features	Strong; automatically learns spatial hierarchies
Performance on Image/Data Types	Moderate; suitable for structured data	Excellent; optimized for image and spatial data
Training Time	Generally faster due to simplicity	Typically longer due to complexity of architecture
Overfitting Risk	Higher risk in smaller datasets	Lower risk due to regularization techniques
Use Case Suitability	Good for general classification tasks	Best for tasks requiring spatial feature recognition
Scalability	Moderate; less efficient for large datasets	High; scales well with increased data complexity
Accuracy	97.61 %	98.64%
F1 Score	94.78%	99%
Precision	93%	99%
Recall	92%	99%

Table 5. Literature Comparison of MLP and CNN for Optical Monitoring and DDoS Detection

Study	Model	Application	Accuracy	Other Metrics
[38]	MLP	Optical Failure Monitoring	97.61%	F1 Score: 94.78%, Precision: 80%, Recall: 80%
[39]	MLP	DDoS Detection	98%	F1 Score: 97%, Precision: 96%, Recall: 96%
[40]	CNN	Optical Monitoring	98 % to 99 %	F1 Score: 99%, Precision: 99%, Recall: 99%
[41]	CNN	DDoS Detection	98.64%	F1 Score: 99%, Precision: 99%, Recall: 100%

C. Economic Benefits of DPUs with Embedded GPUs

Deploying DPUs with embedded GPUs at the network edge offers several key economic advantages: By performing AI-driven tasks such as deep learning inference and optical monitoring directly at the edge, DPUs reduce the need to transfer large amounts of data to centralized data centers, thus lowering bandwidth costs and improving overall network efficiency. Unlike P4-based switches, DPUs come with embedded GPUs that can handle complex AI workloads more efficiently. This is particularly beneficial for tasks requiring deep learning, such as anomaly detection and security threat identification. DPUs offer greater flexibility and scalability as they integrate multiple network functions (security, AI processing, and optical monitoring) in a single unit, reducing the need for additional hardware infrastructure.

D. Comparison with P4-based In-Network Solutions

P4-based in-network computing solutions, while offering programmability and flexibility in handling packet-level operations, do not natively support AI workloads at the network edge. Furthermore, hardware-based switches typically have limited memory and their Arithmetic Logic Unit (ALU) processing power is insufficient for running AI algorithms at the scale required

for tasks like anomaly detection or real-time optical monitoring. Hardware in-network switches are designed to process packets at wire speed, but their memory is highly constrained. These devices rely on small, specialized memory buffers and have a limited number of ALUs, which are well-suited for simple, rule-based operations but struggle with complex AI tasks, especially when large datasets are involved. For instance, in fiber-based ISP-level scenarios or 5G/6G deployments, where vast amounts of data must be processed in real-time, hardware switches are unable to efficiently handle deep learning or machine learning tasks without significant performance degradation. This limitation becomes particularly apparent when dealing with AI tasks requiring high levels of computational power and memory, such as optical failure detection or DDoS attack mitigation, where millions of packets must be analyzed in near real-time.

E. Limitations of In-Network Switches for AI Tasks

In-network switches can handle packet forwarding and basic processing at wire speed, but their performance diminishes significantly when tasked with AI workloads. Given the limited memory and ALU processing power, these switches are not optimized for the intensive computational requirements of machine learning models. For instance, in fiber ISP-level or 5G/6G sce-

Table 6. Comparison of DPUs with Embedded GPUs and P4-based In-Network Solutions

Metric	DPU with Embedded GPU	P4-based In-Network Switch (Software)	In-Network Switch (Hardware)
Price (USD)	\$2,000 - \$4,000 per unit	\$1500 - \$10,500 per unit	\$8,000 - \$15,000 per switch
Throughput	Up to 400 Gbps	Up to 20 Gbps	Up to 6.4 Tbps
Operational Costs	Lower due to reduced data transfer	Moderate due to reliance on external AI	Higher due to large hardware infrastructure
AI Processing Capability	Embedded AI processing with GPUs	Not supported natively	Limited to rule-based processing, not suitable for AI
Memory Availability	Large, supports AI model storage	Moderate, supports packet processing	Limited, insufficient for large AI models
Scalability	High due to integration of multiple functions	Moderate, requires separate AI infrastructure	Low due to reliance on external scaling
ALU Processing Power	Suitable for complex AI tasks	Moderate for basic packet processing	Poor for AI workloads, optimized for simple operations
Power Consumption	Moderate (100W per unit)	Low (50W per unit)	High (300-500W per switch)

narios, where terabytes of data flow through the network per second, hardware-based switches cannot efficiently execute AI algorithms due to their constrained architecture. Consequently, while they offer high throughput regarding packet forwarding, their inability to handle complex AI workloads limits their utility in advanced optical monitoring and security use cases.

- In-network switches have limited memory and ALU power, making them unsuitable for large-scale AI tasks, particularly in scenarios with high data rates, such as fiber ISP-level or 5G/6G networks.
- P4-based in-network solutions are generally more cost-effective from a hardware standpoint, but they lack the embedded AI capabilities that DPUs offer.
- In terms of pure network throughput, hardware-based in-network switches outperform both DPUs and P4-based software switches, making them ideal for large-scale data centers requiring ultra-high-speed networking.
- DPUs excel in integrating AI capabilities directly into the network edge, making them more suitable for environments requiring advanced data analysis, such as real-time optical monitoring and security.
- By offloading data processing to the edge, DPUs reduce operational costs and improve response times for AI workloads. P4-based solutions, on the other hand, may require additional AI infrastructure, thus increasing the overall cost of deployment in AI-heavy applications.

Table 6 compares DPUs with embedded GPUs and P4-based in-network solutions with different metrics such as price, throughput, operational costs, and AI processing capability. In-network switches optimized for packet forwarding at wire speeds have limited memory and ALU processing, making them

unsuitable for AI tasks, especially in high-data-rate environments like ISP-level fiber networks or 5G/6G use cases. DPUs with embedded GPUs provide a more scalable and efficient solution for edge computing tasks that require high throughput and AI capabilities.

9. CONCLUSION

The latest generation of DPUs with embedded GPUs, once equipped with coherent pluggable transceivers, has the potential to enable high-performance packet and optical networking within compact and power-efficient edge computing solutions. In this paper, we present a comprehensive system for monitoring optical failures and detecting DDoS attacks using a DPU with an embedded GPU. Our approach leverages both Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) and deep learning models to provide a robust and efficient solution. The CNN model integration allowed for real-time failure predictions, enabling timely preventive actions. Our results demonstrated a significant reduction in inference time when using DPI.

In the case of DDoS attack detection, we utilized both the DPI custom dataset and the CICDDoS2019 dataset to train our deep learning models. The results indicated that the use of DPI improved the detection system's accuracy, recall, F1 score, and precision. Additionally, the comparison of average inference times between the DPU solution and the DPU with embedded GPU solution underscored the advantages of leveraging hardware acceleration for enhanced performance. The combination of DPI and deep learning models offers a powerful toolset for maintaining the security and reliability of networks. Future work will focus on further optimizing the models and exploring additional use cases for DPI in supporting 5G/6G infrastructures.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.

This work has been partially supported by the EU SNS SEASON Project (101096120) and by the EU under the Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) of NextGenerationEU, partnership on “Telecommunications of the Future” (PE00000001 - program “RESTART”). Work is carried out within the Department of Excellence in AI and Robotics 2023-2027.

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